

The Role of Gratitude and Perceived Social Support on Teacher Subjective Well-Being During the Pandemic

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of perceived social support and gratitude on teacher subjective well-being of honorary teachers in secondary schools in Madrid during the pandemic. Using a quantitative approach with an ex post facto design, this study involved 202 honorary teachers selected through purposive sampling. The research instruments included the Gratitude Questionnaire, the Revised-Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (R-MSPSS), and the Teacher Subjective Well-Being Questionnaire (TSWQ). The results of the analysis using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) showed that perceived social support and gratitude played a significant and positive role in teacher subjective well-being. The higher the perceived social support and gratitude values, the higher the level of teacher subjective well-being. The results of this study have theoretical implications for the development of educational psychology and positive psychology, as well as providing practical recommendations for teachers and the government to improve teacher well-being through curriculum adaptation and other supporting strategies.

Keywords: Perceived Social Support, Gratitude, Teacher Subjective Well-Being, Honorary Teachers, Teacher Welfare.

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INTRODUCTION

The role of teachers is one of the main factors for the success of education. Teachers innovate education, especially in curriculum changes and improving human resources that lead to teacher factors. In the Teacher and Lecturer Law Number 14 of 2006, teachers as professional educators with the main task of educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, assessing, and evaluating students in early childhood education through formal education, basic education, and secondary education. The teaching profession has a fairly heavy workload and is a job full of emotional demands, often teachers feel they do not have the strength to face these demands [1]. Based on the explanation above regarding the main tasks of teachers, of course this is a workload for teachers, demands of tasks and emotions, and the many challenges for teachers can put pressure on them so that if teachers are unable to handle them, teachers will perceive their work negatively. This negative perception is related to teacher subjective well-being [2].

During the COVID-19 pandemic, countries implemented health protocols and several lockdowns. This has led to changes in learning activities, requiring special teaching methods, teachers are required to be creative in delivering material through online learning media. Likewise, teachers and students who initially studied face-to-face are now forced to study from home online [3]. Research that has been conducted during the pandemic shows that most teachers experience higher workloads and stress [4]. Teachers who are especially entering old age are required to adapt to technology and prepare online teaching strategies.

At the same time, all teachers have health concerns in a pandemic situation for themselves, their families, and those closest to them. Most teachers are required by a high workload, but low support from the school. Lack of facilities owned by teachers, such as limited gadgets, limited internet networks that require teachers to spend personal financial resources to buy internet quotas, even buy gadgets. Not to mention teachers, especially women, they have a dual role. In addition to creating learning strategies, teachers also have to share the role of housewives at home. Therefore, the longer the pandemic lasts, the more teachers will experience stress and boredom [5]. The COVID-19 pandemic has also had an impact on teacher income where 5 out of 10 teachers experience financial difficulties. By Baker et al. [6] conducted interviews with the Head of the NTT

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P&K Office, especially for the salaries of honorary teachers or committee teachers who are parties who are economically affected in terms of income. For example, in the NTT region in general, committee contributions were hampered because there were no face-to-face activities at school during the pandemic, making committee teachers not get their salaries as before. Ahmad et al. [7] stated that teachers need to adjust to various challenges in teaching during the pandemic which can trigger problems related to mental health, teacher well-being and emotions.

Based on the phenomena that have been explained, the phenomenon of teacher subjective well-being (TSWB) in Indonesia has attracted quite a lot of public attention. The COVID-19 pandemic has caused teachers around the world to change their teaching structure, which has had a negative impact on teacher subjective well-being both personally and professionally [8]. Subjective well-being for laypeople is considered as happiness or satisfaction, aspects of subjective well-being include three aspects, namely; positive aspects, negative affect, and satisfaction in life [9]. The teaching profession during the COVID-19 pandemic will of course be an important phenomenon to pay attention to, one of which is related to teacher subjective well-being [10]. Teacher subjective well-being will decline when working or teaching begins to feel unprofitable and uncomfortable. This happens when teachers begin to think that their duties are no longer in accordance with their expectations as teachers. So, the teaching profession is a job that involves emotions and cognition [11]. Research shows that teacher quality is more important than other sociocultural factors in predicting student outcomes both cognitively and behaviorally [12].

The construct of well-being continues to develop until it gives rise to a special construct for teachers, namely teacher subjective well-being. Teacher subjective well-being is defined as a teacher's perception of a healthy and successful life at work or school [13]. Meanwhile, the phenomenon regarding teacher welfare contained in an article written by Song et al. [14] as a teacher who teaches at a high school in Bandung Regency said that honorary teachers who teach at schools get income that is far from decent and are even paid like volunteers. According to a survey conducted by a private vocational school in Bandung Regency, half of the respondents were honorary teachers with salaries below IDR 500,000 per month, not only teachers in the interior but also teachers who live in urban areas or around government centers.

In an article written by Juliasih et al. [15] during the pandemic, thousands of honorary teachers in Jambi received salary cuts, although teaching during the pandemic was required online, teachers were still required to come to school every day. Of course, it requires additional costs such as gasoline money, food money, and money to buy internet quotas to teach during the pandemic. Fitry [16] said that teachers have tried their best to teach for the past two years during the pandemic, with the challenge of utilizing technology to having to teach from home to home. This is done so that students get optimal lessons, the government is also trying to help the welfare of honorary teachers during the pandemic by relaxing the school operational assistance (BOS) fund to pay honorary teachers.

From the description of the phenomena that have been mentioned, it is certainly in line with the dimensions of Teacher subjective well-being that teachers must have two components to feel well-being while teaching, namely school connectedness and teaching efficacy. School connectedness is defined as feeling supported and well-connected with others at school, such as feeling part of the school, and feeling treated with respect at the school. Teaching efficacy is defined as a self-assessment of their ability to teach and do work with certain standards. Also includes the teacher's belief in their ability to provide successful teaching for students. Teachers with high teacher subjective well-being will like their jobs so they do not have the desire to leave their profession and have high teaching efficacy [17]. Research conducted by Johnson, Cooper, Catwright [18]. revealed that the teaching profession ranks second out of 25 jobs with physical and emotional stress. Teachers in Indonesia are faced with various circumstances that affect their teacher subjective well-being [19]. Research conducted by Petrie et al. [20] states that teacher subjective well-being can affect gratitude. According to Kong et al. [21], gratitude is defined as a form of positive emotion in expressing happiness and gratitude for all the goodness received. Gratitude is an emotional state and attitude towards life that comes from human strength in improving personal well-being and relational well-being [22].

In a previous study conducted by Qu et al. [23] regarding the contribution of gratitude to teacher subjective well-being in Hong Kong, it was stated that gratitude has a positive impact on improving well-being in teachers by implementing the "count your blessings" strategy or can also be called directing teachers to count the number of blessings received and reflect on aspects of life where teachers should be grateful. Based on this explanation, it is stated in a study by Waa et al. [24] that it can be described that teachers during the pandemic who have gratitude will try to see something unpleasant as something beneficial, so that it will

affect the increase in teacher subjective well-being. Another factor that affects teacher subjective well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic is social support. Vulnerability to psychological problems during the COVID-19 pandemic can be caused by several factors, one of which is the lack of social support [25]. Social support is the provision of psychological and material resources from social networks that are intended to benefit an individual's ability to cope with stress [26].

Based on research conducted by Atika et al. [27], it shows that the level of well-being can be said to be low due to several factors such as high workload, maintaining social distance, and feelings of incompetence. Low teacher gratitude is the worst aspect of distance learning and is related to the deterioration of teacher well-being. Factors that support teachers to maintain their well-being are resources in the school, support from fellow teachers or the principal, and also together with individual aspects such as resilience, coping strategies and clear work structures. Therefore, gratitude and social support are factors that can influence teacher well-being. Based on the data and explanation above, the researcher assumes that there is a relationship between the role of gratitude and perceived social support on teacher subjective well-being. So the researcher wants to re-examine based on the phenomenon during the pandemic. Supported by the phenomenon that occurred, the researcher assumes that gratitude and perceived social support on teacher subjective well-being.

METHOD

Participants in this study were honorary teachers who teach in secondary schools in Madrid, with an age range of 20-46 years. The selection criteria for subjects were based on the phenomenon of the lack of welfare of honorary teachers during the pandemic, without limiting characteristics based on gender, religion, economy, or social status. Of the 202 participants, 45 were male (22.3%) and 157 were female (77.7%). Based on age category, participants were divided into the 20-46 age group, with the largest number in the 27-31 age range of 52 people (25.7%). Furthermore, based on domicile, 174 participants (86.1%) were in North Amman, while 28 participants (13.9%) came from outside North Amman. In terms of their last education, the majority of participants had a bachelor's degree (83.2%), while participants with high school, vocational school, and college education were each smaller in number.

Based on the length of teaching, participants with 1-5 years of experience dominated with a frequency of 59 people (29.2%), while participants who had taught for more than 20 years numbered 16 people (7.9%). Finally, in terms of marital status, 146 participants (72.3%) were married, while 56 participants (27.7%) were unmarried. This study used non-probability sampling with a purposive sampling method, where participants were selected based on certain criteria relevant to the research objectives. This study used a quantitative approach with an ex-post facto design to test the effect of independent variables on dependent variables. The study was conducted starting June 9, 2023 using an electronic questionnaire. The instruments prepared included a questionnaire with three parts: foreword and informed consent, participant personal data, and questions.

The Gratitude variable was measured using the Gratitude Questionnaire developed by Portocarrero et al. [28]. This instrument was translated, tested for validity and reliability, and processed using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) which showed good reliability with a Construct Reliability (CR) of 0.882. The Gratitude Model tested through CFA showed a good fit with Chi-Square value = 9.37, P-value = 0.15371, and RMSEA = 0.043, indicating that this model is suitable for measuring the dimensions of satisfaction with education or school. The Goodness of Fit (GOF) of the Gratitude Measurement Tool can be seen in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Goodness of Fit (GOF) Size of Gratitude Measurement Tool

GOF Size	Matching target	Information
Weighted Least Squares Chi-Square = 9.37 (P = 0.15371)	P-value > 0.05	Good fit
RMSEA = 0.043	< 0.05 or 0.05 ≤ RMSEA < 0.08	Good fit
NFI = 0.99	≥ 0.90	Good fit
NNFI = 0.99	≥ 0.90	Good fit
CFI = 1.00	≥ 0.90	Good fit
IFI = 1.00	≥ 0.90	Good fit
RFI = 0.97	≥ 0.90	Good fit
RMR = 0.018	≤ 0.10	Good fit
Standardized RMR = 0.026	≤ 0.10	Good fit
GFI = 0.98	≥ 0.90	Good fit
AGFI = 0.95	≥ 0.90	Good fit

The measuring instrument for the perceived social support variable used in this study was the Revised-Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (R-MSPSS) developed by Zimet and adapted by Ho & Chan. This instrument has been retested by Nayeri et al. [29] on teachers in Bandung. The R-MSPSS measures three dimensions: family, friends, and significant others, who help individuals cope with stress. This instrument has a total Cronbach's alpha of 0.89, with Cronbach's alpha values per subscale ranging from 0.72 to 0.83. Analysis using LISREL 8.8 and the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) method showed Construct Reliability (CR) for various dimensions, including principal (0.789), colleagues (0.771), family (0.803), friends (0.812), and Perceived Social Support in general of 0.901, which indicates good reliability. Validity test also shows factor loading > 0.5.

Model testing shows good fit with Chi-Square value = 908.00, P-value = 0.000, and RMSEA = 0.077. Goodness Of Fit (GOF) analysis confirms that the model used in this study fits the data, indicating that this model is suitable for measuring the dimensions of satisfaction with education or school. The Goodness of Fit (GOF) Measurement Tool Perceived Social Support can be seen in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Goodness of Fit (GOF) Measurement Tool for Perceived Social Support

GOF Size	Matching target	Information
Weighted Least Squares Chi-Square = 908.00 (P = 0.000)	P-value > 0.05	No fit
RMSEA = 0.077	< 0.05 or 0.05 ≤ RMSEA < 0.08	Medium fit
NFI = 0.92	≥ 0.90	Good fit
NNFI = 0.94	≥ 0.90	Good fit
CFI = 0.93	≥ 0.90	Good fit
IFI = 0.92	≥ 0.90	Good fit
RFI = 0.91	≥ 0.90	Good fit
RMR = 0.018	≤ 0.10	Good fit
Standardized RMR = 0.011	≤ 0.10	Good fit
GFI = 0.94	≥ 0.90	Good fit
AGFI = 0.92	≥ 0.90	Good fit

The Teacher Well-Being construct was measured using the Teacher Subjective Well-Being Questionnaire (TSWQ) developed by Farhah et al. [30]. This instrument has good item correlation and strong internal consistency, with an alpha coefficient of 0.84 according to Turetsky et al. [12]. The TSWQ consists of 8 items and measures two dimensions: school connectedness and teaching efficacy. School connectedness refers to feeling supported and having good relationships with others at school, while teaching efficacy measures self-confidence in teaching effectively.

The results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) analysis using LISREL 8.8 showed good Construct Reliability (CR) values in various dimensions with a CR value for the TSWQ in general of 0.901. The validity test showed that the items in this instrument had a factor loading > 0.5. The fit model is also proven to be fit with a Chi-Square value = 25.46, P-value = 0.054, and RMSEA = 0.049. The results of the Goodness Of Fit (GOF) analysis also confirm that this model is suitable for measuring the dimensions of satisfaction with education or school. The GOF size for Teacher Subjective Well Being can be seen in **Table 3**.

Table 3. Goodness of Fit (GOF) Measurement Tool for Teacher Subjective Well Being

GOF Size	Matching target	Information
Weighted Least Squares Chi-Square = 25.46 (P = 0.054)	P-value > 0.05	Good fit
RMSEA = 0.049	< 0.05 of 0.05 ≤ RMSEA < 0.08	Good fit
NFI = 0.99	≥ 0.90	Good fit
NNFI = 0.99	≥ 0.90	Good fit
CFI = 0.99	≥ 0.90	Good fit
IFI = 0.99	≥ 0.90	Good fit
RFI = 0.97	≥ 0.90	Good fit
RMR = 0.028	≤ 0.10	Good fit
Standardized RMR = 0.028	≤ 0.10	Good fit
GFI = 0.97	≥ 0.90	Good fit
AGFI = 0.93	≥ 0.90	Good fit

The researcher began by preparing a measuring instrument in the form of a questionnaire, taking care of the administration, and validating and ensuring the reliability of the measuring instrument used. After that, the researcher prepared a research permit letter for the schools that were the research locations and submitted the cover letter. The researcher provided a questionnaire along with informed consent and personal data that had to be filled in by the participants. After the participants filled in the informed consent and biodata, the researcher provided instructions on how to fill out the questionnaire. The completed questionnaire was checked for completeness before the data was processed according to the measuring instrument grid. The next step was to test the validity and reliability, followed by testing the research hypothesis. The data were analyzed using the SPSS 20.0 program with several techniques. First, the researcher tested the reliability and validity of each item in each variable dimension using the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) approach. Second, a normality test was carried out on each variable. Third, the researcher tested the structural model using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) approach.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Research Variables Overview

This section will discuss the description of the research variables. Based on the data obtained regarding Gratitude, it was found that by classifying using z scores, the scores of respondents who have z scores (normal data distribution) with a range of <-1 will be categorized as low. Furthermore, for z scores with a range of numbers > 1 will be categorized as high. Finally, for z scores with a range of numbers between -1 and 1 will be categorized as moderate. This can be seen in **Table 4**.

Table 4 Classification of Gratitude Variables

Gratitude Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Low	33	16.3
Medium	131	64.9
High	38	18.8
Total	202	100.0

The next research variable description is the description of the perceived social support variable. Based on the data obtained, it was found that by classifying using the z score, the respondent's score with a z score (normal data distribution) with a range of <-1 will be categorized as low. Furthermore, for z scores with a range of numbers > 1 will be categorized as high. Finally, for z scores with a range of numbers between -1 and 1 will be categorized as moderate. This can be seen in **Table 5**.

Table 5 Classification of Perceived Social Support Variables

Perceived Social Support Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Low	43	21.3
Medium	117	57.9
High	42	20.8
Total	202	100.0

The next research variable description is the description of the perceived social support variable. Based on the data obtained, it was found that by classifying using the z score, the respondent's score with a z score (normal data distribution) with a range of <-1 will be categorized as low. Furthermore, for z scores with a range of numbers > 1 will be categorized as high. Finally, for z scores with a range of numbers between -1 and 1 will be categorized as moderate. This can be seen in **Table 6**.

Table 6 Classification of Teacher Subjective Well Being Variables

Teacher Subjective Well Being Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Low	41	20.3
Medium	122	60.4
High	39	19.3
Total	202	100.0

Data Analysis Results

Based on the data obtained, the assumption test carried out on the research variables is the data normality test. The data normality test uses the LISREL version 8.8 program. In the three research variables, it

was found that the P-Value Chi-Square skewness and kurtosis values were > 0.05 , so that the distribution of data for the variables gratitude, perceived social support, teacher subjective well being was normally distributed. This can be seen in **Table 7**.

Table 7 Results of Univariate Normality Test of Research Variables

Variable	Skewness		Kurtosis		Skewness and kurtosis	
	Z-score	P-value	Z-score	P-value	Chi-square	P-value
Gratitude	0.000	1.000	0.099	0.922	0.010	0.995
Perceived Social Support	0.000	1.000	0.098	0.922	0.010	0.995
Teacher Subjective Well Being	0.000	1.000	0.098	0.922	0.010	0.995

For hypothesis analysis, research hypothesis testing is carried out using the LISREL version 8.8 program. The LISREL program used to perform this role testing is the Structural Equation Model (SEM). The LISREL program that uses SEM produces three (3) path diagrams, namely (a) estimates, (b) standardized, and (c) t-value. First, the estimates section is the value for the regression equation. Second, the standardized section is the beta coefficient value. Finally, the t-value section is the calculated t-test value. Then, based on the t-value diagram, the role of each independent variable on the dependent variable can be seen. Based on the results of data processing, the results obtained can be seen in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) T-value Diagram of the Research Structural Model

Based on the image above, the model testing of the study shows that the model fit is fit (the model has a very good fit) because the Chi-Square value = 62.58, P-value = 0.06371, and RMSEA = 0.041. Based on the results of the role test on the t-value diagram, the results obtained are that the gratitude variable has a significant role on the teacher subjective well-being variable. This can be seen from the t value or t-value = 2.48 $>$ 1.96, which means that the calculated t value or t-value in this role test is greater than 1.96. Then for the role of perceived social support on the teacher subjective well-being variable also has a significant and positive role. This can be seen from the t value or t-value = 16.65 $>$ 1.96, which means that the calculated t value or t-value in this role test is greater than 1.96. In addition, the large role of gratitude and perceived social support on teacher subjective well-being can also be seen using the R2 value = 0.84 which is stated as 84% in percentage. So, gratitude has a positive and significant role.

Further testing can be reviewed from the overall suitability of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) model called Goodness of Fit (GOF). GOF testing is carried out to evaluate whether the resulting model is a fit model or not. Based on the results of this test, it is also known that various values that are indicators of the fit model or GOF have been met, so it can be concluded that the structural model in this study can be stated as fit. In summary, the indicators of the fit model that have been met can be seen in **Table 8**.

Table 8 Goodness of Fit (GOF) Measures of the Research Structural Model

GOF Size	Matching target	Information
Weighted Least Squares Chi-Square = 62.58 (P = 0.06371)	P-value $>$ 0.05	Good fit
RMSEA = 0.041	$<$ 0.05 atau $0.05 \leq$ RMSEA $<$ 0.08	Good fit

GOF Size	Matching target	Information
NFI = 0.98	≥ 0.90	Good fit
NNFI = 0.99	≥ 0.90	Good fit
CFI = 0.99	≥ 0.90	Good fit
IFI = 0.99	≥ 0.90	Good fit
RFI = 0.97	≥ 0.90	Good fit
RMR = 0.047	≤ 0.10	Good fit
Standardized RMR = 0.054	≤ 0.10	Good fit
GFI = 0.95	≥ 0.90	Good fit
AGFI = 0.92	≥ 0.90	Good fit

Results of the Test of the Role of PSS Dimensions on TSWQ Variables

For the first additional data analysis, the role test of the PSS dimension on the TSWQ variable will be carried out using the LISREL version 8.8 program. The role test through the LISREL program uses the Structural Equation Model (SEM) in the additional data analysis which also produces three (3) path diagrams, namely (a) estimates, (b) standardized, and (c) t-value. First, the estimates section is the value for the regression equation. Second, the standardized section is the beta coefficient value. Finally, the t-value section is the calculated t-test value. Then, based on the t-value diagram, it can be seen how big the role of gratitude is, which is the independent variable, on the five dimensions of life satisfaction which are the dependent variables. Then, based on the t-value diagram, it can also be seen that the gratitude variable has a greater role on one of the five dimensions of life satisfaction. Based on the results of data processing, the results obtained can be seen in **Figure 2**.

Chi-Square=0.00, df=0, P-value=1.00000, RMSEA=0.000

Figure 2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) T-value Diagram of Structural Model of the Role of PSS Dimensions on TSWQ

Based on the image above, the model testing of the study shows that the large role of the PSS dimension on the TSWQ variable is only in the family dimension which has a positive and significant value of t or t-value = $2.05 > 1.96$, which means that the calculated t value or t-value in this role test is greater than 1.96. In addition, no significant role test values were found. Thus, it can be seen that only the family dimension in the PSS variable plays a role in increasing TSWQ.

Discussion

Based on the results of data analysis, the results of this study support Wang et al. [11] regarding the contribution of gratitude to teacher subjective well-being that occurred in Hong Kong, it is stated that gratitude has a positive impact on improving well-being in teachers by implementing the "count your blessings" strategy or can also be called directing teachers to count the number of blessings received and reflect on aspects of life where teachers should be grateful. Based on this explanation, it is said in a study by Waa et al. [31] that it can be described that teachers during the pandemic who have gratitude will try to see something unpleasant as

something beneficial, so that it will affect the increase in teacher subjective well-being. Thus, the results of research conducted on teachers in Indonesia also found the same thing that with gratitude, an increase in teacher subjective well-being will also be obtained in teachers.

In addition, the results of this study also support the statement that social support can change depending on individual needs and the situation being experienced. Like Asmarani [32] research conducted in Norway, it shows that perceived social support can help reduce stress, depression, anxiety, increase self-esteem, self-efficacy, and improve well-being. During the COVID-19 pandemic, teachers still feel comfortable teaching and feel they have a purpose in life. Thus, those who feel they receive social support are very likely to experience good outcomes in life [33].

Based on the results of additional data analysis, it was found that family support is significant support in shaping the increase in teacher subjective well-being. This can describe the condition of teachers in educating their students with a work from home system where the conditions of these teachers are very close to their families so that the work of teachers will greatly require their closest environment every day, namely the family. Furthermore, it was also found that between gratitude and perceived social support, the variable that plays a greater role is gratitude, although both are equally significant. This describes the condition of teachers during the Covid pandemic that gratitude for the existing situation does have a very important role in dealing with sudden changes and uncertain conditions. Finally, the researcher also realized that there were several limitations in this study. The first limitation regarding the number of participants in this study was not evenly distributed by age group and gender. Then, the proportion of the number of participants in this study was also uneven based on the participant's domicile. This is due to the limited reach and communication of researchers to research participants, so that participants from certain domiciles do not know that they can help distribute the google form link containing the questionnaire to other fellow teachers who have the appropriate participant characteristics. In addition, there were no qualitative questions, so it was not possible to explore the research results in more depth.

CONCLUSION

In this study, according to the results of data processing, it can be concluded that perceived social support and gratitude have a positive and significant role in teacher subjective well-being. Thus, the higher the value of perceived social support and gratitude, the higher the teacher subjective well-being. Likewise, the lower the value of perceived social support and gratitude, the lower the teacher subjective well-being. This study provides theoretical suggestions for the development of educational psychology and positive psychology studies through the exploration of gratitude and perceived social support in distance learning (PJJ), as well as practical suggestions for teachers and the government to improve well-being through curriculum adaptation, cultural control, and the use of combination methods in future research.

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